

اسلامی قانون میں اصول تعبیر و تشریح (انگریزی اصول تعبیر کے ساتھ ایک تقابلی جائزہ)

PRINCIPLES OF INTERPRETATION IN ISLAMIC LAW (A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS WITH ENGLISH PRINCIPLES OF INTERPRETATION)

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ABSTRACT

The Qur'an and the Sunnah are the two main sources of Islamic law. The texts of the Qur'an and Sunnah are so comprehensive and extensive that the limited texts of the Qur'an and Sunnah provide solutions to the infinite problems that will arise until the Day of Judgment and this is possible only through the interpretation of the texts. However, this interpretation of the text is bound by certain principles and rules, which were in view of the Companions of the Prophet (PBUH) and the Muslim Jurists. Such principles and rules are called the Principles of Interpretation of Islamic Law.

This article discusses the nature and scope of the principles of interpretation of Islamic law and sheds light on their origins and evolution. It also describes the nature and scope of the principles of interpretation of English law and provides a comparative analysis of both. It has been proven in the article that the art of interpreting the laws is in fact the invention of Muslim Jurists and the English principles of interpretation are based on Islamic principles of interpretation which had been elaborated long ago by the Muslim Jurists in a more detailed, concise and disciplined manner.

Keywords: Islamic Law, Fiqah, Jurisprudence, Law, Interpretation.

کلیدی الفاظ: اسلامی قوانین، فقہ، قانون، قانونی نص، تعبیر و تشریح۔

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